

SOCIAL ESSENCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya. Jismoniy tarbiya pedagogik jarayon hisoblanib, u keng qamrovli ta'lim-tarbiya, sog'lomlashtirish va mehnatga tayyorlash kabi muhim jarayonlar o'z ichiga oladi: Jismoniy tarbiyaning ijtimoiy ahamiyati deganda quyidagi bog'liqliklar va vazifalarni tushunish lozim: uning aqliy, estetik va mehnat tarbiyasi bilan bog'liqligiga qisqacha ta'sir berish mumkin. Jismoniy tarbiya har bir soha yoki jarayonning mazmuni va yo'nalishiga qarab, aqliy tarbiyani rivojlantirishda xizmat qiladi. Masalan: sportda yoki artistlarning (balet) muz ustida figurali uchishlarida yo'nalishlarni va necha marta aylanishlarni bilishlari aqliy jihatdan boshqarilishini his etishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: mashg'ulot, aspekt, jismoniy, mentalitet, sog'liq, ta'lim, sport, kuch, harbiy, rivojlanish, tana, faoliyat.

Аннотация. Физическое воспитание-это педагогический процесс, который включает в себя такие важные процессы, как воспитание, оздоровление и подготовка к труду: под социальным значением физического воспитания следует понимать следующие взаимосвязанные работы и задачи: можно кратко затронуть его связь с умственным, эстетическим и трудовым воспитанием. Физическое воспитание служит для развития умственного воспитания в зависимости от содержания и направленности каждой отрасли или процесса. Например: в спорте или фигурном катании артистов (балет) на льду знание направлений и количества вращений-это чувство, что ими можно управлять мысленно.

Ключевые слова: тренировка, аспект, физический, менталитет, здоровье, образование, спорт, сила, военное дело, развитие, тело, активность.

Abstract. Physical education is considered a pedagogical process, it includes such important processes as comprehensive education, wellness and preparation for Labor: the social significance of physical education means that the following related-likes and tasks should be understood: its mental, aesthetic and labor education can be briefly influenced by the link. Physical Education serves in the development of mental education, depending on the content and direction of each area or process. For example: in sports or artists' (ballet) figure skating on ice, it is to feel mentally controlled that they know the directions and how many turns.

Keywords: training, aspect, physical, mentality, health, education, sports, strength, military, development, body, activity.

INTRODUCTION

The social essence of physical education is understood as an increase in the ability to work. This provides for production Gymnastics, various exercises during intermediate breaks-Games, sports training on the day of rest, trips and other direct services. The role of physical education in the implementation of aesthetic education has its own characteristics. It is expressed in such games as dances, ballet, circus, percussion. In the art of singing, physical exercises are also widely used in the ways of deep-breathing, tempering the throat passages with fresh air. Artistic, Rhythmic (aerobics) gymnastics, trampoline jumping, water swimming, underwater Gymnastics

(synchronized swimming), ice skating and other areas include artistry, aesthetic aspects related to physical education and sports.

Discussion and results

In order to improve health from physical education and sports, the health-improving forces of nature (water, air, sun) and hygienic requirements are fully observed. For this reason, from the embodiment of natural and special processes associated with human activity in the socio-educational characteristics of physical education and sports. Physical education and sports as an important branch of the Commonwealth it is an important tool that serves to increase the health and working capacity of the population. At its core, socio-economic processes such as human upbringing, physical perfection, cultural recreation are embodied. Sport as the peak of physical education has its own socio-economic characteristics.

Selection of talented young people, testing them-from experiments transfer and develop sports skills to the level of a skillful athlete requires strong scientific and practical work. Means of physical education and sports production in labor processes (industry, construction, agriculture, etc.) improve employee health, work broad path in order to increase the ability and, most importantly, physical conditioning are being put in. In educational institutions, preschool and various other institutions physical education and sport is a socio-educational process of state significance being used as. Such mass health-improving physical education-sports a number of laws and government decisions aimed at organizing their activities are practically their own it pays off. In the new organization of physical education and sports in our country the most advanced experiences and scientific, research of our country and world sport the results are widely used in life. Physical education and sports in the scientific organization of Labor[1,7]

The scientific organization of Labor has two tools:

1. Research;
2. Testing the newest and most advanced experiments and getting positive extensive application of results are performed.

Activities of constant involvement in physical education and sports are mainly two is realized in the direction, i.e.:

1. In direct production processes (labor equipment, actions, Organization of Special-Field (professional) exercises.

2. At leisure (except work) independently loved, knew practice games. This includes living and working areas, in sports facilities specially organized various sports competitions, hosting favourite games, participation in them in public.

In the socio-educational features of physical education and sports wellness activities are a socio-pedagogic process that plays an important role. On this basis, he specializes in physical education and sports training of personnel is an important process that is subject to state education.[3] This, in turn, is in the physical education and sports movement satisfaction of needs, further socio-cultural conditions of the population related to improvement. Along the way, the president and the Republican government the activities carried out by are giving its high level of effectiveness. For this reason, physical in all segments of the population the number of people involved in one type or another of upbringing and sports is growing increasing. And this is the socio-educational in physical education and sports from the essences of its properties. Raising young people in our country in the spirit of military patriotism serious attention was paid to the work, and above all the neighborhoods, educational institutions, workers work on education in production enterprises, institutions great attention is paid to strengthening. [12]

Military-patriotic concepts and practical activities for it, mainly implemented in the following directions:

1. In all types of educational institutions with adolescents, they are called military preparedness training up to conscription die cotton.
2. "Patriot " assisting military organizations activities of the organization.
3. District/city military commissariats.
4. Neighborhoods and families.

Military-Physical Training in the above directions the content of its events includes exercise, Sports, Travel (Tourism, marking and etc) and targeted use of folk National Games.[10] Their some can be given a brief description:

1. Physical education classes. High schools of general education classes and physical held in secondary special and higher educational institutions the content of upbringing classes, mainly students-young people physically

1. aimed at being harmonious and genuine. Gymnastics in it, light from elements of athletics, water swimming, wrestling and other sports used.

2. Special in pre-conscription military training classes physical conditioning in the content of technical and tactical preparations also has its own has a substitute. In this case, tension on the turnstile, hanging, spinning, medium and long distance running, swimming in the water, testing wrist strength, from obstacles jumping and other exercises are widely used.

3. At military call points (district-city military commissariats) to test physical fitness and the future Organization of training for training soldiers in special physical training.

4. Military units, types in units and specialization depending on, military training is carried out.

5. Constantly passing with officers and senior officers activities that provide the physical fitness to go to.

The phrase development is primarily associated with the initial state of the organs of the human body (body) and the degree of its growth (development). It is basically a derivative of a wide range of natural and special processes, such as biological, physiological, biochemical, psychological, physical education. Development is a process of quantitative and qualitative changes in the human body. The result of development is the coming of age of man as a biological species and social being. The biological species in a person is characterized by physical development, includes morphological, biochemical, physiological changes.[2]

Social development, on the other hand, is seen in psychological, spiritual, mental development. If a person develops to the extent that it allows him to be called conscious, capable of independent activity, he is called a person. A person is not born a person, but matures as a person in the process of development. The concept of personality is a social description of a person, it shows the characteristics that are formed under the influence of social relations, communication with other people. As a person, a person is formed in the social system with the help of a goal-oriented and well-thought-out upbringing. The individual is identified, on the one hand - through the acquisition of social experience, and on the other - through the Giving of material and spiritual wealth to society. To become a person, a person must be able to show his inner characteristics, which are endowed by nature in activity and practice and formed through life and upbringing.[8,9]

Human development is an extremely complex, long-lasting and contradictory process. There are changes in our organism throughout our lives, but mainly the physical and inner world of a person actively changes in childhood and adolescence. The development of quantitative

change is not a simple drawing and a straight line movement from bottom to top. The attentive side of this process is the transition of the physical, psychic and spiritual sides of the individual to quantitative changes. Human development is a natural uncontrollable process, development does not depend on the conditions of life. Unlike animals that get used to life very slowly, a person creates the necessary tools for living with his own labor.

In the national model of Personnel Training, a person is defined as the main subject and object of the personnel training system, the consumer of the following services of education and their implementation. The following state policy of Personnel Training provides for the intellectual and spiritual-moral education of a person, the achievement of his manifestation as a comprehensively developed person. The implementation of this social requirement guarantees the right of each citizen to receive knowledge, to demonstrate creative abilities, to develop intellectually and to work in a specific professional direction.[4,5,6]

The science of Physical Education, Sports, Travel, people's national games, like all disciplines, plays an important role in the development of student youth mentally and physically and the development of life - suitability. Physical development refers to the fact that all organs of the body are healthy, perform movements compactly and quickly. This in turn is composed of a number of physical qualities, such as agility, agility, strength, endurance, flexibility. They develop by means of morning Gymnastics, physical education classes, sports training (training), preparation for sports competitions and participation in it.

CONCLUSION

In the development of the physical aspect, the maturation of the harmonious generation, all activities (functions) in the human body and their upbringing are of pedagogical importance. The intense (acute) period of physical development corresponds to the pre-school and junior school age period and lasts throughout the school age period. In practice, we come across the phrase indicators of physical development. It is the size of the wrist of the organs of the human body and is listed in the manner of anthropometric data on the physical development of the person involved or individual.[11]

The direction, character, level of physical development, as well as the qualities and abilities that a person matures in himself largely depend on living conditions and upbringing. The acquisition of the laws of physical development, their use for the purposes of self-education, is an important task of the theory and practice of physical education. Social conditions in society are a decisive factor in their physical development. Among the factors, the role of the process of training with Labor is important, especially the role of physical education. To achieve development, the body began to use the so-called "Physical Education", a specially oriented and organized activity.

REFERENCES

1. Железняк Ю.Д. Основы научно-методической деятельности в физической культуре и спорте. - М.: Академия, 2013.
2. Железняк Ю.Д. Теория и методика спортивных игр. Учебник для студентов вузов. - М., Академия, 2013.
3. Матвеев Л.П. Основы общей теории спорта и системы подготовки спортсменов. - Киев, Олимпийская литература, 1999.
4. Axmatov M.S. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida ommaviy sport-sog'lomlashtirish ishlarini samarali boshqarish. T.: 2005. – 142 b.
5. Axmedova M.E" Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi" o'quv qo'l. -T. Tafakkur-bo'stoni 2011 y.

6. Abdumalikov R., YUnusov T. va boshqa. "O'zbekistonda jismoniy tarbiya ta'limining rivojlanishi". Metodik tavsiyanoma. T. O'zDJTI, 1992 yil
7. Vardanyan A.N. Pedagogika fizicheskogo vospitaniya i sporta. Metodicheskie rekomndatsii. - 2010 yil
8. Kerimov F.A. Sport sohasidagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar. T. Zarqalam. 2004 yil
9. Maksimenko A.M. Pedagogicheskaya praktika studentov po fizicheskomu vospitaniyu v shkole. M. Fizicheskaya kultura 2006 god
10. Metodologiya sovremennoy obshchey sportivnoy pedagogiki materialy Vseros. nauch. kon. M. Evsti 2004 god
11. Neverkovich S.D. Pedagogika fizicheskoy kul'turuy i sporta M. «<Akademiya>> 2010 god
12. Tursunov U. "Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi" o'quv qo'llanma Qo'qon 1992 yil